

**Market Value Estimation of Football Players: A
Metaheuristic Machine Learning Approach
Incorporating Performance Metrics, Injuries and
Club Stature**

A Project Report submitted in fulfilment of the requirement for the
award of the degree of Bachelor of Science in Economics

Submitted By
Mr. Anay Shukla
BECO22209

Under the supervision of
Prof. Aseem Bhagwat
Assistant Professor
Gokhale Institute of Politics and Economics

Gokhale Institute of Politics and Economics
Pune 411004

Declaration

I, Mr. Anay Shukla, declare that this dissertation entitled is the outcome of my own study undertaken under the guidance and supervision of Prof. Aseem Bhagwat, Gokhale Institute of Politics & Economics, Deemed University, Pune. It has not previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma or certificate of this Institute or University. I have duly acknowledged all the sources used by me in the preparation of this dissertation.

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This is to certify that the dissertation entitled, is the record of the original work done by Mr. Anay Shukla bearing PNR BECO22209 under my guidance and supervision. The result of the research presented in this project report have not previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or the certificate of this Institute or of any other Institute or University.

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Abstract

Football has witnessed unprecedented monetary growth over the years, enabling clubs to have higher purchasing power, which along with rapidly rising number of talented players, has given birth to a booming interest in player evaluation. Market value fluctuates depending on player performance and enables clubs to establish a clearer monetary threshold for any player when they aim at attempting a transfer. Crowd/forum-based estimates, formulated through discussions have been used as a reference point for long, but machine learning predictive models are on the rise due to the subjectivity and potential biasedness of the crowd estimates. This paper is aimed at predicting market values of players in Europe's top 8 Leagues across the span of their career till date. The novelty of this paper stems from extensive usage of statistic-based performance metrics along with novel injury metrics as features in ML models employed which comprised of eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Random Forest Regression and Support Vector Regression (SVR). The models were enhanced with 4 different metaheuristic algorithms, Genetic Algorithm (GA), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), Dwarf Mongoose Optimization (DMO) for feature selection, with the DMO-XGB models yielding MAPE values of below 2%, indicative of its high predictive accuracy.

Keywords: Market Value, Performance Metrics, Machine Learning, Metaheuristic Algorithms, European Football Leagues.

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Contents

List of Figures	6
List of Tables	7
List of Equations	8
1 Introduction	9
2 Literature Review	10
2.1 Historical overview	10
2.2 Market Value vs Transfer Value	12
2.3 Market Value Estimation and Determinants Research	13
2.4 Usage of ML in developing predictive models	15
2.5 Injuries being under-researched	16
3 Research Gap and Objectives	17
4 Data	18
4.1 Overview	18
4.2 Performance Metrics	19
4.2.1 Shooting Metrics	21
4.2.2 Per 90 Metric and Penalties	24
4.2.3 Passing Metrics	25
4.2.4 Pass Types	30
4.2.5 Possession Metrics	31
4.2.6 Goal and Shot Creating Action Metrics	34
4.2.7 Defensive Metrics	35
4.2.8 Goalkeeping Metrics	36
4.2.9 Miscellaneous	37
4.2.10 Non-Performance Metrics	38
4.3 Injuries	39
5 Methodology	40

5.1	Overview	40
5.2	Feature Selection	41
5.3	Metaheuristic Algorithms	44
5.3.1	Genetic Algorithm	45
5.3.2	Particle Swarm Optimization	48
5.3.3	Ant Colony Optimization	52
5.3.4	Dwarf Mongoose Optimization	55
6	Empirical Results	58
6.1	Model Evaluation	58
6.2	Non-Goalkeepers Dataset	61
6.3	Goalkeepers Dataset	62
6.4	Feature Importance	63
6.5	Player Predictions	66
7	Conclusion	69
	Appendix: Glossary for Performance Metrics	70
	General Metrics	70
	Miscellaneous Stats	71
	Shooting Metrics	72
	Passing Metrics	73
	Pass Types	74
	Goal and Shot Creation	75
	Defensive Actions	76
	Possession	77
	Goalkeeping	78
	References	79

List of Figures

1	Division of the main playing positions into 21 roles with arrows to show interlinked duties between the roles (Aalbers & Haaren, 2018)	20
2	Shot Map for Chris Wood in the 24/25 Premier League Season till 30th January (Source: Author's Github Repo: (Shukla, 2024)) . . .	22
3	Shot Map for Yoane Wissa in the 24/25 Premier League Season till 30th January (Source: Author's Github Repo: (Shukla, 2024)) . . .	23
4	Shot Map for Dominic Calvert-Lewin in the 24/25 Premier League Season till 30th January (Source: Author's Github Repo: (Shukla, 2024))	23
5	Division of a Football Pitch into Thirds	25
6	Passing attempts per90 across positions in 2024 in the top 8 leagues (Data: (FBref.com, n.d.)	26
7	Pass completion % across the positions in 2024 in the top 8 leagues (Data: (FBref.com, n.d.))	27
8	Completion Rates (in %) of different pass types across the positions in 2024 in the top 8 leagues (Data: (FBref.com, n.d.))	28
9	Passes attempted per90 of different types across the positions in 2024 in the top 8 leagues (Data:(FBref.com, n.d.))	28
10	Comparing the creative performances of Andy Robertson and Trent Alexander Arnold of Liverpool using the xA metric (Whitmore, 2021)	29
11	Average Touches per 90 by Position and Zone for the 2023-24 season (Data: (FBref.com, n.d.))	32
12	Pitch visualization of average Touches per 90 by zones for the 2023-24 season (Data: (FBref.com, n.d.))	33
13	Average Defensive Metrics per90 by Positions for the 2023-24 season (Data: (FBref.com, n.d.))	36
14	Correlation Matrix of the features in the goalkeeper data	42
15	Correlation Matrix of the features in the non-goalkeeper dataset . .	43
16	Crossover between two chromosomes, (Holland, 1992)	45
17	Comparison of different selection techniques (Katoch et al., 2021) .	47

18	Genetic information swapping after a two-point crossover(Katoch et al., 2021)	48
19	Flowchart illustration of the process of the PSO algorithm (Wang et al., 2018)	51
20	Graphical depiction of failures witnessed per different weights (Shi & Eberhart, 1998)	52
21	Deneubourg’s bridge (a) and Goss’ Bridge (b) (Dorigo et al., 2006)	53
22	Pictorial Representation of the foraging behaviour utilized in DMO (Agushaka et al., 2022)	56

List of Tables

1	Performance Comparison of the Machine Learning Models (Non-Goalkeepers)	60
2	Performance Comparison of the Machine Learning Models (Goalkeepers)	60
3	Feature Importance of the Selected Machine Learning Models (Non-Goalkeepers)	64
4	Feature Importance of the Selected Machine Learning Models (Goalkeepers)	65
5	Highest Valued Players from the Non-Goalkeeper Testing Dataset	66
6	Highest Valued Players from the Goalkeeper Testing Dataset	67
7	Top 5 Overestimated Players from the Non-Goalkeeper Testing Dataset	68
8	Top 5 Underestimated Players from the Non-Goalkeeper Testing Dataset	68
9	Top 5 Overestimated Players from the Goalkeeper Testing Dataset	68
10	Top 5 Underestimated Players from the Goalkeeper Testing Dataset	68

List of Equations

1	Fitness function	46
2	Change in velocity based on the bird's personal best position from coordinate x	48
3	Change in velocity based on the bird's personal best position from coordinate y	49
4	Change in velocity based on the swarm's personal best position from coordinate x	49
5	Change in velocity based on the swarm's personal best position from coordinate y	49
6	Change in velocity after communication	49
7	Basic PSO Algorithm	49
8	Inertia in velocity calculations	50
9	Inertia in the basic PSO algorithm	50
10	Probability of an ant choosing the first bridge	53
11	Probability of an ant choosing any component	54
12	Pheromone update	54
13	Quantity of pheromone deposited	55
14	Alpha score	57
15	Potential food source calculation	57
16	Sleeping mound value of each iteration	57
17	Average sleeping mound value	57
18	Scout mongoose simulation	58

1 Introduction

Football has been a game appealing to many, due to its simplicity of understanding and exciting, fast-paced games; bound to give any viewer a dopamine rush. The growth of this sport is owed to the foundation of football clubs across the various countries, some spanning over a hundred years and more, and some newly founded clubs paving the way for the newer generations as well. Now, several decades since its inception, clubs have now amassed huge followings and viewership, enabling higher number of sponsorships and funding; making it a business generating high revenue. The generated revenue is then used to develop and enhance stadium capacities, boosted to accommodate 50,000+ people, providing those watchers with refreshments and hosting concerts and other large-scale events to earn even higher profits; however questions arise

Club football also requires high capital outflows for sustainability. Investments in building a state-of-the-art training ground and related facilities are essential to develop a holistic work atmosphere for the players to strengthen team cohesion and enhance their skills or develop new ones. Despite, these heavy investments, the most amount of the expenditure of any club is on the weekly wages and on player transfers. Player transfers are necessary every season, to bring in players, either for squad depth reasons or to improve quality of the squad by signing a high potential or an experienced player. Transfers also generate income in terms of player sales, making it even more essential aspect for a club.

Earlier, before FA (Football Association) professionalized, players could play for more than one clubs and were not bound by contracts (Classic Football History of the Game, [n.d.](#)). Later, professionalism came into the picture as players demanded remuneration, which caused the FA to start registering all players; bidding them to the clubs they were playing for. However, a player could transfer to another club only if the current club is willing to let the player leave. This system was soon abolished due to player objections regarding freedom of choice.

The earliest known transfer fees usually ranged below £100, but in 1893, Willie Groves joined Aston Villa from West Bromwich Albion for £1000 (Barclay, 2014). Gradually, the fees started increasing to five figures in 1928, and by 1961, Ballon d’Or winner Luis Suarez became the first player to be sold above £100000 (Sport, 2013). The current transfer market has now reached exorbitant amounts, top clubs and their players being valued in hundreds of millions.

Keeping demand and supply factors aside, how these player values are estimated is an intriguing field of research. Questions which arise in my mind are simplistic yet definitive, such as how accurate these models have been, or what explanatory variables are being factored and which have been excluded. This paper seeks to comprehensively understand the crucial aspects involved in making such models, single out the flaws and attempt to create a model of my own to assess a football player’s value; factoring into account new variables which the popular models do not consider.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Historical overview

The economic and statistical scope of research in sports, especially association football, can make it a particularly novel research prospect. Sloane (1971) was one of the first papers to delve into this area in detail, elaborating on how a club’s expenditure mechanism functions. He insisted that clubs should not be viewed as profit-maximizing bodies, rather as “utility maximizing” models with the aim to take the club to greater heights, in terms of achievement. Some clubs generate positive returns, but most operate at a loss due to the exorbitant fees paid in player transfers. However, due to the paradox of competition in football, clubs gain mutual advantages from rival clubs performing well such as increased match attendances and television viewership. Plus, if losses from signing expensive but

talented players enable the club to ensure long-run survival, then its next goal would be to achieve a break-even point.

Madden and Robinson (2012) further developed on Sloane's founding, factoring account rising fan involvement in club governance. They formed a model over club objectives/utility functions such as profits generated, winning percentage and supporter welfare, with the findings suggested that a profitable club results in social sub-optimality as ticket prices rise to sustain such profits and the inverse resulting in lowered ticket prices. A fan-governed club at a break-even point is a good thing as the revenue generated from increased ticket sales can be devoted to player expenditure/new signings, allowing for higher performances in the league.

The earliest literature in estimating transfer values empirically is credited to Carmichael and Thomas (1993), talking about the institutionalized structure of bargaining and negotiation in finalizing transfer fees. They proceeded with 7 different equations in a basic cross-sectional data, taking proxy variables for factors affecting transfer fee such as age, goals scored, position and goal difference of both the buying and selling clubs, positional dummies etc. A thing to be noted is that they estimated factors influencing the finalized transfer amount paid/received by the club, and most of these factors non-performance metrics; much rather linked to the stature, success in the league. Reilly and Witt (1995) followed up on this paper, but with the focus on assessing the possibility of racial discrimination affecting transfer fees. The findings were inconclusive as there was inadequate evidence to confidently conclude that race of a player leads to unfair transfer fees in contrast to their counterparts.

Another data driven approach was adopted by Carmichael et al. (1999), as they now emphasized on player performance metrics from the past years (with respect to their position) and how it determined the odds of the player being transferred and later estimating transfer fees paid. They were able to conclude that the probability of a player transferring is not random, as factors such as goals and age impact it significantly. Speight and Thomas (1997) went a step ahead, focusing on the arbitrage fees of such deals empirically, showcasing that an arbitrator is more

likely to focus on the individual characteristics of the player in question, so as to justify his value and not just find an even ground for resolution between clubs.

Szymanski and Smith (1997) argued that the transfer valuation process is competitive in nature, reliant on minimum fee acceptable to the selling club or circumstances, which is in contrast to Carmichael and Thomas (1993), who considered it to bargaining to be the crux in the determination of transfer fees. Dobson and Gerrard (1999) developed an econometric model to understand the inflation in transfers, suggesting a rise of 11.6% annually (which is outdated in modern times), accredited to their model consisting of player traits and club characteristics (buying or selling club) and time effects, and it conveyed that transfer valuation is highly systematic, paving way for further exploration with such models. Papers with such empirical models to evaluate transfer values/salaries were compiled and analysed by Frick (2007), which can be referred to for further depth. However, the novelty of his work was finding out the lack of contract duration taken into the models, along with the subtle discrimination in play for players from different leagues.

2.2 Market Value vs Transfer Value

Before proceeding further in this field, it needs to be made clear that there is a distinction between market value and transfer value. This conundrum is brilliantly addressed by Poli et al. (2022), pointing out how some papers present in this literature [with the example of Serna Rodríguez et al. (2019)], term market value as a proxy for the wages or the finalized transfer fees paid. He et al. (2015) also believed that these values are comparable and did use transfer fees to replicate market values in his Lasso Regression. Müller et al. (2017) did commendable work in his FE models but contradicted his statements regarding the relation between transfer fees and market value, initially citing He et al. (2015) to call them comparable but ending it with saying there are conceptual difference.

Market value is more of proxy meant to highlight performance and potential ability of a player, along with factors such as publicity. Market value can help clubs decide on a transfer fee, but the other way around is certainly not possible. For e.g. a player bought at an exorbitant fee fails to perform to the expectations set for him, so his value as an asset shall fall, thus making transfer fees not a true representative of the player's value. Thus, to provide absolute clarity, this paper will solely focus on market value, not deviating to salary and transfer fees or other such variables. Market value's importance for a player is derived from its ability to be a close proxy to salary, and in some situations even transfer fees, but mainly an indicator of performance.

2.3 Market Value Estimation and Determinants Research

The most commonly referred source for market values by media outlets and even scientific research, is Transfermarkt ([n.d.](#)); where community discussions and debates determine the market value of a player. The site is open to all, with only registration being the requirement to participate. A member can start a thread regarding changing a specific player's market value with valid reasoning (such as any attribute of that player) and other members can give their inputs, however the final decision lies with the discussion leader, who are just members with higher merit and experience. They act as the final judge, weighing upon every member's vote according to their accord. Seemingly, this system might be influenced by biases due to no democratic structure (as in, the votes are not equivocal) and popular choice thus, leading to members to not favour true performance indicators.

Herm et al. ([2014](#)) found out that the online community-based market values perform well and are highly predictive of the actual transfer fees, which is a positive finding to squash doubts regarding the method's viability. Findings in Peeters ([2018](#)) also concluded that there is no evidence to back the claim of overvaluing popular players due to wishful thinking bias, rather appreciating it as an integral source to be utilized in forecasting/predictive models. Müller et al. ([2017](#))

compared their data-driven estimates with the Transfermarkt estimates, yielding that crowd estimates being only slightly more accurate. To account that these trends are in line with lesser popular leagues, Frick and Prockl (2018) calculated market value estimates for MLS (Major League Soccer) and arrived at the similar conclusion, praising the accuracy of the crowd estimates.

Frick (2006) in his RE and FE models used market value derived from Transfermarkt and modified them to make them a proxy for player annual salaries. Garcia-del-Barrio and Pujol (2007) talks about the monopsonist angle, questioning how clubs are not generating profits from the player rents, taking log-transformed market value of La Liga player and running OLS models to prove it empirically, with conclusive findings showing how bargaining power rests with the few extremely talented players. Similarly, Bryson et al. (2013) run an OLS regression taking market value as a proxy for undisclosed salary, finding that a premium exists for players who are two-footed (players who are comfortable playing with either of their feet). However, all these papers used market value as a proxy and never tried to estimate them. Herm et al. (2014) estimated the impact of talent and external variables on market value, in a bid to assess the accuracy of Transfermarkt's market values. Affirming the claims stated earlier in performance-market value relations, He et al. (2015) used a Lasso regression model to estimate market value of La Liga players using performance indicators only. Though focused only on estimation of forwards, the findings reveal significant impact of performance indicators.

As market value estimates gained momentum in literature, further development in understanding factors affecting player valuation has been researched. Albeit some of these papers (Gulbrandsen & Gulbrandsen, 2011; Majewski, 2016; Ruijg & van Ophem, 2015; van den Berg, 2011) are estimating transfer fees/salaries, the determinants involved in their respective models provide an overview of determinants affecting market value as well, accounting for the closeness of terminologies. The common determinants which turn out to have significant impacts include age, age 2, goals scored, positional dummies and club stature, with only van den Berg (2011) using injuries in his multivariate model. Injuries do need to be accounted for as they affect the ability of a player to perform, directly which impacts their

transfer appeal, even-post recovery. We do need to note that interpretation will be different in comparison to market value, due to transfer fees being the finalized fees agreed upon by clubs, thus bargaining and competitive frameworks coming into the picture, which has no effect on market value estimation.

Trushnikova (2022) did divide her dataset into attackers and defenders, taking varying performance metrics related to specific positions, such as interceptions and aerial duels (labelled as ‘Air Fight’ in the paper). However, her subsets do not account for Goalkeepers, Midfielders or Wingers, who play different roles altogether, thus clustering them will lead to inaccurate results, positionally. Poli et al. (2022) created a model for CIES to estimate transfer values as well, with similar variables but with some exceptions, notably youth performances, a determinant certainly hard to account for.

2.4 Usage of ML in developing predictive models

Exclusive market value estimation has been done by quite a few papers in recent years. Elahi et al. (2023) analysed papers who established models to do such estimations, highlighting their findings and shortcomings. A critique mentioned by them was the usage of generic performance metrics instead of positional-specific metrics, which I highlighted as well. Majewski (2021) with his FGLS model established importance of popularity and appeal of a player as a brand, a commodity of sorts which can generate a stream of revenue for the club, i.e. through jersey sales, better attendance, meet and greets etc. Zhou (2019) does factor positional differences through mean, but does not apply it in his OLS model. Drawbacks of such models are that they do not provide accuracy nor depth in predicting future market values.

Machine Learning (ML) algorithms have been developed and applied to produce far more accurate estimations in comparison to its traditional counterparts. Dias (2020) ran Random Forest on cross-sectional data of players, comparing the models

fit, one without factoring in previous year's market value versus the other including, with former showing a better fit. Random Forest is also used by C. Li et al. (2022) to predict salaries and creating a variable called 'Total Grade' to account for club ranking affecting player status. Even though they take a variable for the positions, it still fails to account different metrics for each position. Behravan and Razavi (2021) used FIFA 20 (the video game) attributes of each player to factor in positional-specific metrics. They also used APSO (automatic particle swarm optimization) clustering to divide the players into separate clusters based on their positions and then run an automatic regression to filter features that are relevant, so that the model can be trained. The Support Vector Regression (SVR) ran showcased a good fit and strengthens the reliance on ML for such predictive work. Different ML models can yield different and potentially better fits (Sun & Gu, 2024). They ran 3 different ML models and had similar usage of attributes from a FIFA game with Random Forest having the best fit out of all.

2.5 Injuries being under-researched

Injuries occur in all sports, but more frequently to the physical intensity and aggression required in the game, leading to fouls causing bodily harm, along with fatigue sustained from the games played. All clubs spend a hefty sum on their medical staff, as they aim to preserve and enhance healing of their 'assets'. Ekstrand (n.d.) found out a correlation that the higher number of matches played resulted in increased odds to get injured, with Rubio-Martín et al. (2022) claim that the market value of renowned players starts reducing after three injuries, showing that physical resilience is valued. Injuries do hamper performance, thus making it a potent risk to any player's market value (Leifheit & Follert, 2021). Injury proneness going unnoticed will yield market values which are not a true representative of the player, as they are not directly contributing to the team. However, players with great physical conditions are highly valued and their values do not fall tremendously with a few injuries, but if the injury is severe, the drop in price is significant and will continue to deteriorate until the player improves in

their physical condition (Martín et al., 2024).

Even though this field has seen relative development across the years there remain shortcomings to be solved and new horizons to be explored. It would be incorrect to call this area of literature new and unscratched, but this paper aims at unearthing novel ideas and applying them to develop a potential breakthrough in predictive modelling of market values.

3 Research Gap and Objectives

The research gap witnessed in this field is not regarding accuracy as most of these papers tend to have good fitting models. However, all of these models lack one determinant or the other, such as position-specific subsets and performance metrics, to acknowledge positional-fee disparities. Injuries is another such factor not seen across the models, which is when heightened to the level of proneness, will decrease the appeal of a player and hampers their ability to perform too. Usage of expected statistics (xG, npxG and xA) is limited and not applied efficiently either, along with other metrics such as progressive passes, save percentage. These positional-metrics ought to a better proxy to help understand the performance of a player on the pitch.

Based on these, the objectives of this thesis are as follows:

- Understand the performance metrics, both generic and position-specific, in depth
- Applying such metrics as the features to account with a special focus on injuries, along with club and league stature, in the predictive model
- Developing a predictive ML model using different approaches and choosing the one which can estimate the most precise market values of football players.

4 Data

4.1 Overview

Data is obtained through web-scraping, mainly through two different sources, FBref.com (n.d.), for performance metrics of each player (generic and positional-specific), and Transfermarkt (n.d.), for player injuries and pre-existing market values across their playing career. The reason for factoring in these variables is due to the increased accuracy obtained from quantifying such variables (Singh & Lamba, 2019). To account for other variables such as club and league rankings, which varies per confederation, certain sites have been taken which have compiled rankings, with FootballDatabase (n.d.) for club rankings and league rankings based upon the net worth of the leagues from Transfermarkt (n.d.). Data involves players playing in the top 8 European Leagues based on their market value worth, which are:

1. Premier League (English Top Division)
2. La Liga (Spanish Top Division)
3. Serie A (Italian Top Division)
4. Bundesliga (German Top Division)
5. Ligue 1 (French Top Division)
6. Liga Portugal/Primeira Liga (Portuguese Top Division)
7. Eredivisie (Dutch Top Division)
8. Süper Lig (Turkish Top Division)

Most papers consist of traditional performance metrics such as Goals scored, Assists provided, Tackles, Cleansheets etc. Some papers do delve into predictive

metrics such as xG and xA, but none go in depth regarding different positional metrics. FBref.com ([n.d.](#)) has different statistic tables based on in-game actions such as goalkeeping, passing, defending, creating, shooting etc., with unique variables across all. Lőrincz ([2022](#)) utilized such variables a multiple linear regression, but prioritized attackers only, focusing on their performance metrics. Other positions and their metrics shall be focused upon as well in this paper.

4.2 Performance Metrics

Performance Metrics involved in the dataset can be broadly divided into generic and positional metrics. Generic metrics involve features which are commonly used to assess a player. However, it is possible for generic metrics to be used interchangeably with positional metrics as these can carry certain weightage dependent on the role. For example, racking up the yellow cards is an event faced by all players, irrespective of their position, but the weightage it carries varies. For defenders, yellow cards received will be expected to be higher due to frequent indulgence in tackles and acting as the last man if necessitated, but for forwards, it could be indicative of recklessness or lack of composure in duels.

Positions in football can also be broadly divided into 4 categories: Goalkeepers (GK), Defenders (DF), Midfielders (MF) and Forwards (FW), with the GKs and the DFs playing in the defensive third, the MFs in the middle third and the FWs in the final third. Each position has its own specific role and instructions, thus needing for separate metrics to assess them accurately. In layman terms, it would refer to associating GKs with goalkeeping metrics, DFs with defending metrics, MFs with creative metrics and FWs with shooting metrics. However, football positions are more nuances than just simply linking respective positional metrics, as there are roles which might have a DF be further up ahead in the final third, producing higher creative actions or a FW with higher successive tackling rates. Aalbers and Haaren ([2018](#)) divided these positions into 21 roles based on roles seen in Football Manager, a game revered for its realism. Figure 1 presents a graphical

Figure 1: Division of the main playing positions into 21 roles with arrows to show interlinked duties between the roles (Aalbers & Haaren, 2018)

overview of the same presented by them, affirming the existence of nuanced role. Goalkeepers do also have nuanced roles but usually are not as complex as the rest and is the only categories to not be connected to the others.

Thus, this establishes the need to have an approach involving the separation of goalkeepers as a separate dataset and accommodate the rest of the players in one dataset. To accomplish this, inclusion of shooting, passing (and related metrics such as possession) and defending metrics have been taken for all DFs, MFs and FWs, creating a total of 127 performance metrics for each player. Thus, before proceeding with the ML framework, it becomes essential to establish concrete definitions for the metrics, but it does become tedious to delve into detail for all 127 of them: hence the approach now being explanations of the key concepts to develop a base to understand the rest of the metrics due to the inherent linkage between them. Detailed definitions of the metrics utilised can be found in [Appendix](#).

4.2.1 Shooting Metrics

Shots and goals scored are popular metrics with respect to shooting as it is something visible to naked eye, one of the core concepts of the game and part of even the earliest predictive models, however the most common predictive metric in regard to shooting is Expected Goals (xG). The novelty of this metric is that it is a better attempt at handling noise in a game like football, in comparison to a simple metric such as a shot, which as a standalone metric, is unable to highlight the quality of the shot. xG assigns a probability of scoring a goal to a shot taken, depending on plethora of factors influencing it, essentially acting as an expected value.

xG is modelled based off historical data and predicted using different ML techniques such as logistic regression, SVMs, gradient boosting (XGBoost) etc. These models take into account variables such as distance and angle of the shot, type of the shot (set pieces such as penalties, freekicks, corners, header etc.), etc. Thus, different models use different factors, including or excluding some, and hence they differ in their xG values. Like almost any other variable in football, xG is subject to inaccuracies as this game consists of a lot of noise, making it hard for any predictive metric to have high precision and also the fact the goals are a Boolean event (goal or no goal) (Mead et al., 2023).

Another perspective to this situation could be perhaps that Wissa is able to position himself in such a way which allows him to even attempt such high xG shots, indicative of sharp awareness and decision-making skills. However, there can be situations where underperformance can be so extreme, attributing it to poor finishing, as seen in Figure 4 with Everton striker Dominic Calvert-Lewin. Calvert-Lewin has witnessed an underperformance of an astonishing (-) 4.85 xG or by (-) 61.9 %. Surprisingly, Calvert-Lewin also has more shots than Wood, but if you notice most of his shots are of lower quality or xG.

Figures 2 and 3 depict shot maps of 2 strikers in the Premier League, Yoane Wissa

Figure 2: Shot Map for Chris Wood in the 24/25 Premier League Season till 30th January
(Source: Author's Github Repo: (Shukla, 2024))

and Chris Wood, both having reached a double-digit goal threshold, with Wood having 4 more goals than Wissa. The size of the circle in the shot map is proportional to higher xG, i.e. bigger the size, higher the xG and vice versa. Both players have similar number of total shots taken too, but their total xG accumulated have a difference of 2.09, with Wissa having the edge. Wood is outperforming his xG (the positive difference between total goals scored and total xG accumulated) by 4.34 or by 44.9% whereas Wissa is underperforming his xG by (-)1.75 or by (-) 14.89%. Such a stark contrast in these 2 players can only be highlighted by a metric such as xG, but the interpretations can still be inaccurate. Suggesting that Wood is a prolific finisher and Wissa lacks in that department would be an unfair judgement, as it is entirely possible that Wood's positive variance regresses back to the mean and so does Wissa's negative variance.

Figure 3: Shot Map for Yoane Wisna in the 24/25 Premier League Season till 30th January (Source: Author’s Github Repo: (Shukla, 2024))

Figure 4: Shot Map for Dominic Calvert-Lewin in the 24/25 Premier League Season till 30th January (Source: Author’s Github Repo: (Shukla, 2024))

4.2.2 Per 90 Metric and Penalties

Minutes played is a discrepancy often not covered by normal metrics, causing comparison between players with more minutes played versus a player with lesser minutes played due to reasons such as injury or being a fringe player. The per 90 (p90) metric equalizes such differences by factoring basic metrics on a per game basis (which is just 90 minutes played), allowing for fairer comparisons and also rewarding coming off the bench performance. If the xG p90 is 0.53, it is usually interpreted as that the player is expected to score 53 times in 100 games. However, it is also important to acknowledge that this metric alone can also skew perceptions and needs to be paired with minutes played as well to reward consistency as well.

Penalties tend to disrupt xG patterns as they act as outliers, due to a guaranteed high xG shot at all times due to the nature of this set piece. OPTA accounts a penalty shot to have a floor of 0.76 xG, thus need for a metric to deal with this skewness, a challenge tackled by npG (Non-Penalty Goals) and npxg (Non-Penalty xG). These metrics exclude penalties in their calculations, enhancing comparability among the players. Separating penalties also allows for assessing the penalty scoring ability of a player with more emphasis on the frequency of penalties converted.

In our strikers' comparison itself, it is intriguing to note that Calvert-Lewin has a higher npxG p90 (0.44) than Wood (0.39), but this difference is not even remotely reflected on the goals scored by Calvert-Lewin. Wissa outclasses them in almost every single underlying metric and thus should be valued accordingly, especially being trigger happy (i.e. not hesitant to shoot often as indicated by the high Shots per 90) and averaging a xG per shot of 0.25. Another thing to note is that these comparisons should be made with the same positional cohort, as the attacking threat of strikers will be significantly higher than the defenders and to assess the attacking threat of defenders, it needs to be within their respective cohorts.

Thus, every performance metric, which is essentially majority of the features in the

Figure 5: Division of a Football Pitch into Thirds

dataset, will be a per90 (except the ones where it is not possible to do so such as Shot on Target %, which being a percentile variable is not affected by the minutes played).

4.2.3 Passing Metrics

To achieve the target of scoring a goal, moving the ball around without losing it is crucial to the process. Teams require players who excel in successfully placing these passes and thus creating opportunities to score. A valid assumption that can be made is that these metrics are useful to assess the performance of midfielders as they are tasked to be the creative and linking outlets in the team but, a football field is divided into thirds (refer to Figure 5), where positionally, midfielders tend to occupy the middle third and gradually moving the ball ahead to the offensive or the final third, to progress the attack. However, since the defensive and final thirds are occupied by the defenders and forwards respectively, completing successful passes becomes an important trait for them too.

Passes and ball progression in football occur through several pass types and scenarios, varying in the action causing it to occur or the chance it creates. The most

Figure 6: Passing attempts per90 across positions in 2024 in the top 8 leagues (Data: (FBref.com, n.d.)

basic metric of passing is, passes attempted and completed. This metric can be commonality among the positions despite the importance of it varying between the positions. The simplicity of this metric however can be misleading if not taken into account the subtypes of passes that occur on the pitch. As seen in Figure 6, defenders ('DF') have more passing attempts in a match (per 90 metric used) than midfielders ('MF'), with forwards ('FW') having the fewest attempts, averaging around 20 passing attempts per90 (or in a match). Another argument could be made regarding the accuracy and completion of the passes to assess the quality over quantity which is illustrated by Figure 7, but most defenders do average around 80%+ rate of completion, a bit higher than the midfielders.

Passes can be divided into 3 types depending on the distance between the passer and the intended receiver:

- Short Passes: Passes occurring between 5 and 15 yards,
- Medium Passes: Passes occurring between 15 and 30 yards,
- Long Passes: Passes occurring longer than 30 yards.

Figure 7: Pass completion % across the positions in 2024 in the top 8 leagues (Data: (FBref.com, n.d.))

Thus, ideally making short passes having the highest odds of being accurate due to the short travelling distance making it less prone to errors (assuming *ceteris paribus*). However, factoring these types into account does not affect the completion rate of defenders but rather enhances it. Figure 8 depicts a high average completion rate of short and medium passes for both defenders and midfielders, but with midfielders do edge out the defenders with respect to long passes completion rate, which is fleshed out better in Figure 9, which highlights the lesser frequency of medium and long passes attempted by the midfielders and yet achieving similar or higher completion rates than the defenders, indicative of their skill which is a prerequisite for their role, producing quality over smaller amounts of quantity.

To understand the cause behind the high passing numbers showcased by the defenders over the other 2 positions in terms of sheer quantity, one needs to delve into tactical and match analysis frameworks. In Gama et al. (2016), they analysed 30 matches in a season of a particular team in the Primeira Liga (Portuguese Premier League/First Division) to understand passing networks and possession. The second highest amount of possession interaction by a player was by a central defender, followed by the left fullback (in layman terms, the defender responsible of the left flank, occasionally progressing play ahead with marauding runs down the

Figure 8: Completion Rates (in %) of different pass types across the positions in 2024 in the top 8 leagues (Data: (FBref.com, n.d.))

Figure 9: Passes attempted per90 of different types across the positions in 2024 in the top 8 leagues (Data:(FBref.com, n.d.))

flank or to the centre). The passing network map highlights the extensive amount of passing interactions taking place between the defenders and the midfielder, explaining the high quantity of short passes by the defenders. Their findings also show very few unsuccessful interactions in the defensive third, with majority of it occurring in the middle third due to the opposition's press and attempts to tackle the ball away, explaining the higher short and medium pass completion rates of the defenders and higher quantity of passes attempted by the midfielders yet lower completion rates.

The idea behind high number of passes originating from the defence can be ac-

Figure 10: Comparing the creative performances of Andy Robertson and Trent Alexander Arnold of Liverpool using the xA metric (Whitmore, 2021)

credited to tactical playstyle or specific game situations which demand a defensive possession orientation. Successful teams often tend to maintain high levels of possession in both the defensive and offensive halves but only in the scenario of an eventual transitional play to attempt to score. Unsuccessful teams, however, retain more possession in the defensive third and especially so when they are losing. Intention can also define such orientations, for instance a successful team intending to draw in a particular match would maintain the tempo and have longer possession in the defensive zones (Casal et al., 2019).

The other metrics taken into account are measures of creativity of a player, which tend to have higher weightage on central/attacking midfielders along with wingers and inside forwards. Expected metrics do occur in this section, out of which, technically only one metric is truly derived in a similar fashion to that of xG. As OPTA defines it, Expected Assists (xA) are the odds of how likely a pass can lead to a goal depending on the type, distance, phase of play etc. which is much like its goal-related counterpart. The edge xA has over traditional metrics is the ability to showcase the quality of the pass rather than the final outcome (Whitmore, 2021).

Using OPTA data, a side-by-side comparison of the attacking fullbacks of Liverpool during their recent title-winning season highlights quality which is often hidden by other metrics. Robertson and Alexander-Arnold played key roles in

guiding Liverpool to the trophy, establishing themselves as creative yet defensive powerhouses. Taking a glimpse at assists in Figure 10, it would seem that Robertson was creatively better than his right sided counterpart, having produced 10 assists from open play (all plays in the game excluding set pieces) with Arnold only producing 6 assists. However, their xA suggests that Arnold had better quality of chances created than Robertson, who overperformed his xA (almost double the expectations).

The other expected metric used is xAG (Expected Assisted Goals). This metric measures the xG of the shot which is followed by the pass which is assisting the shot. xA measured the odds of a pass leading to goal whereas xAG is more refined and xG-based, measuring the likelihood of the shot being a goal rather than the pass creating one. Usage can be interchangeable depending on the interpretation needed. The other metrics involved are traditional metrics such as Key Passes, Passes into the Final Third, Passes and Crosses into the Penalty Box and Progressive Passes. These metrics provide a far more quantitative view of creative, which might not highlight but perhaps could be indicators of determination to generate creative output.

4.2.4 Pass Types

Subdividing pass types based on distance covered does not highlight the differences that occur in different scenarios. Live ball passes refer to passes happening during open play whereas dead ball passes are passes which happen from set pieces such as freekicks, corners, throw-ins, goalkicks etc. In a recent study of the 2018 World Cup, it was found that out of the 169 goals scored in the tournament, 40.24% of the goals (i.e. 68 goals) were scored from set-pieces, with 22 of those originating from corner kicks and 21 from free kicks, showcasing the importance of effective set-piece deployment to gain the upper hand (Göral, 2019). Similar such findings were found for EURO 2012, where 22 (28.95%) out of the 76 goals were scored from Stopped Balls (SB), which is another term for Dead Balls or Set Pieces (Leite,

2012). However, a point to note would be that these studies have mainly been done on tournaments, thus calling for the need for a perspective on the league format. In Fernandez-Hermogenes et al. (2020), top 5 teams from La Liga and La Liga 2 were analysed based on the 52 matches played to assess the impact of set pieces attacking play (SPAP). Their findings, on the contrary to the tournament-based papers, claimed that set pieces had limited effectiveness, but did not disregard the impact it can have on the match result rather suggesting a training regime to enhance such plays. Thus, it becomes detrimental to account for players with specific traits which suit such set piece play.

Even in live ball scenarios, crosses are essential to create chances. The quality of crosses can be measured through xA and xAG (refer to Section 4.2.3), the quantity of such passes is accounted for too (normalized to per90, similar to all eligible metrics). Another Boolean metric to assess the quality of crosses can be attesting whether the cross was completed (i.e. connected with the intended target) or were blocked or offside (depending on the front man's position, it could be attributed as an error of the crosser). Other metrics to assess technical skills of a player are switches, which are long crosses over 40 yards to switch flanks where the passage of play will occur. Pertsukhov and Shalenko (2021) used traditional metrics to assess which quantitative indicators represent the ability of the best players in different roles. Through balls were considered to be one of such attributes which the best midfielders excelled at. Through balls refer to passes which split open defences, as the ball traverses in between in the gaps. It is an important skill to highlight creative vision too, as it shows the awareness of the midfielder. Such balls are played when the player knows his teammate will be making a marauding run to get the pass played.

4.2.5 Possession Metrics

Possession-related metrics are broadly divided into touches, carries, take-ons and receives. Touches by a player are indicative of the presence of the player in the

Figure 11: Average Touches per 90 by Position and Zone for the 2023-24 season (Data: (FBref.com, [n.d.](#)))

build-up play and proactiveness. However, touches are affected by the role/position of the player and touches can also vary from location to location. For e.g. a forward usually will not be expected to have a lot of touches as he is supposed to spearhead the attack. But his number of touches in the areas occupied by him such as the final third or the opposition's penalty area could be relatively higher than his other teammates on the pitch. Touches in specific locations highlight the areas occupied by the players, enabling the creation of heatmaps.

Figure 11 gives a clearer image of the relativeness of touches in the zones based on positions. Defensive positions have the higher amount of touches in their own penalty area (Def Pen) and the defensive third (Def 3rd) in comparison to the rest. Purely DF roles average around 22.68 touches per 90 in the defensive 3rd, a figure which FWs can only achieve 2.05 due to their role requiring to be staying up ahead. Middle third (Mid 3rd) witnesses a drastic increase in the touches by

Figure 12: Pitch visualization of average Touches per 90 by zones for the 2023-24 season (Data: (FBref.com, n.d.))

all positions, affirming the importance of control over the middle third. Figure 12 provides a similar overview but with pitch zonal division and no positional divide. The average touches per90 being the highest in middle third (21.6) confirms the claim made above. Interestingly enough, averages number of touch per90 in the opposition's penalty area (Att Pen) is the lowest at 1.9, which is a plausible number as Figure 12 does not account for the positions thus, skewing the number to be lowest as the presence of defenders and most of the midfielders will not be up ahead in the pitch. It can also be attributed the defence of the opposition heavily fortifying/guarding that region and logically pressing higher to intercept any threatening ball towards their goal.

Forwards do not exhibit high quantities of touches in a game. Even in the attacking third (Att 3rd), they average 11.13 touches per90, a number below the average as seen in Figure 12. However, FW (along with FW, MFs) outperform others in the opposition's penalty area due to them being the focal point of attack. A FW with fewer touches in the box and yet being able to shoot, score and create chances indicates the quality required due to the unavailability of the quantity

being supplied or created. Such positional touch trends and disparities are also exhibited by the best performing players (Pertsukhov & Shalenko, 2021).

OPTA defines Carries as “player moving the ball five metres or more” with a Progressive Carry being “carries that move the ball more than five meters up field” (Analyst, 2024). Carries showcase the dribbling skills and the ability to retain the ball further up ahead in pitch where the opposition has a man advantage to thwart the attack and win back the ball. Such technical skills are useful to judge primarily the wingers and wingbacks, along with midfielders who can drop deep and dribble past opponents to create an attacking threat. A specific scenario during a carry occurs, known as a take-on, where the dribbler takes on the opponent defender (could also be any other position not necessarily a defender) in one-on-one.

If the dribbler successfully dribbles past the defender it’s considered to be a successful take-on whereas if the opponent wins the ball or if the dribbler retains the possession instead of dribbling past, it is considered an unsuccessful take-on for the dribbler. Take-ons utilise the technical skillset of the player as it involves trickier scenarios such as dealing with tight pockets of space and predicting the move of the defender, which in comparison to carries which occur on the pitch, require higher utilization of the aforementioned skillset. Passes received indicate the importance of the player in the passing/possession network, with the players on the higher side being the centroid of the play, acting as a pivot point where all passes go through before turning into a full-fledged attack.

4.2.6 Goal and Shot Creating Action Metrics

A metric solely meant to assess creativity, Shot Creating Actions (SCA) and Goal Creating Actions (GCA) differ solely on the outcome of the actions, i.e. SCA leads to a shot and GCA leads to a goal. Actions imbibed in these terms can refer to a plethora of actions that can occur in a game such as take-ons, crosses, through balls, set pieces, tackles etc, therefore not limiting to actions done more

frequently by players up ahead but players all over. Subdivision of such actions can provide an insight into which action a player might excel at which enables him to create such chances. For e.g., a player who specialises in corner delivery will have a higher SCA/GCA per90 originating from dead ball scenarios. It is similar to xA and other creative metrics, but its vantage point is more interpretability of a player's attributes due to the subdivision of the actions.

4.2.7 Defensive Metrics

The only metric focusing on the defensive aspect of a player's performance and like the other metrics, it needs subdivisions to understand the depth of defending. Defending broadly involves tackling, blocking and intercepting. Tackling refers to attempting to win possession back from the opponent and is considered a successful tackle only when the player gets the ball back to his team. Blocks involve putting one's body in the way to stop a shot which is on target (heading towards goal) whereas a blocked pass involves restricting a pass from being completed. An interception is the term given to an intentional attempt to block the pass and return possession of the ball back to your team. Clearance refers to getting the ball away from a threatening zone with no intended target.

As the name suggests, such metrics carry higher weightage for defenders, but defensive actions are required to some extent at every position, as seen in Figure 13. Defenders do lead almost all the metrics, but even in those the gap is extremely narrow. Defenders average 1.1 interceptions per90 which is only 0.2 ahead of the defensive midfielders (DF, MF) and midfielders (MF). All positions except the forwards (both FW and FW,MF) average 0.7 blocks per90, with 85.7% (0.6 out of the 0.7) of that figure originating from passes blocked for the midfielders whereas it's a more even split for the defenders with 57.1% of their average coming from shots blocked, which can be considered to have higher impact due to the threat shots incur. Clearances are dominated by defenders as they are the last line of defence, but defensive midfielder also average 1.3 clearances per90. Tackles won

Figure 13: Average Defensive Metrics per90 by Positions for the 2023-24 season (Data: (FBref.com, n.d.))

per90 is dominated by the midfielders but a point to note is the number of tackles attempted by the defenders must be fairly larger and thus reducing the average. Challenges lost are the counterpart of take-ons, with the point of view of the defender attempting to tackle the ball away. Defenders average the lowest among all the positions, showing quality of the tackling and the ability to win balls easier than more.

4.2.8 Goalkeeping Metrics

Unlike the rest of the positions, goalkeepers do not have heavily nuanced differences in their subdivided roles and barely share any commonalities with the rest of the positions, hence I have kept a separate dataset for the goalkeepers involving goalkeeping metrics. Goalkeeping metrics involve figures to assess the shot-stopping ability of the goalkeeper. Goals Against (GA) refer to the number of goals conceded by the goalkeeper, with per90 metric being goals conceded every game. Shots on Target Against (SoTA) involve shots which the goalkeeper faces

inclusive of the SoT that result in goals, with Saves then being derived from the difference between SoTA and GA. Saves% is the measure of successful saving attempts made by the keeper. The primary aim of the goalkeeper is to not concede a goal throughout the match, which is called a clean sheet (CS). Clean sheets are often credited to a goalkeeper 's performance but there are cases where defenders perform better and therefore not letting shots in for the goalkeeper to stop, making clean sheets a combined effort.

Penalties are crucial set pieces to defend as they are heavily attacker favoured, especially based on the xG (Refer to Section 4.2.2). Goalkeepers are also assessed based on the Penalty kicks saved and penalty kicks allowed, with penalty kicks conceded being usually higher due to the disadvantageous situation they are in but having penalty kicks saved indicates composure and fast reflexes.

4.2.9 Miscellaneous

Some metrics are commonalities to all the positions, events which happen across the games. Fouls are committed or drawn by all players, with committed fouls treated with a negative connotation and foul drawn with a positive connotation. Fouls are penalised through warnings from the referee, followed by a yellow card which is the final warning, and finally a red card. If a player received a second yellow card, it is counted as a red card and the player is sent off and cannot continue the rest of the game. A direct red card showing has the same effect but is also followed with a suspension for the next match or more, depending on the severity of the foul committed. Wright and Hirotsu (2003) provided a new perspective to fouls and cards received, calling them professional fouls. They claimed that players committed fouls which would aid the team, and the referee penalises the player rather than the team, therefore resulting in a potential gain for the team. Aggression becomes a coinflip event dependent on the game situation. The other fouling related attribute would be conceding a penalty, i.e. the player committed the foul which led to the penalty occurring. Similarly, a penalty won refers to the

player who won the foul which led to his team getting a penalty.

Offsides refers to when an attacking player is ahead of the deepest defender before the ball has been played. Offsides result in a free kick for the defending team and are considered erroneous for the attacking team. For a forward, frequently venturing into offsides could be a sign of bad game awareness and thus hindering performances. Own goals happen when a player unintentionally scores into his own net. It should be considered as an event of negative variance (or misfortune) as most of the times it is caused due to deflections and rarely because of heinous errors.

Aerial Duels refer to challenges by two opposing players to get ball which is up in the air. This metric is mostly dominated by the taller players, who naturally have a higher jumping reach. It becomes crucial for the forwards who aim to score headers and for the defenders who aim to defend such aerial crosses and also enhance their own corner goalscoring attempts.

4.2.10 Non-Performance Metrics

Physicality of player does matter on the pitch but there is no proxy to measure it. The only physical features which are included are height (in cm) and the weight (in kg) and these do tend to influence performances such as ability to win headers and ability to out physical somebody to win back the ball. As discussed earlier in the literature review, club stature and league's outreach does affect the player's performance. Performing in a difficult competitive environment should generate higher value and the club's net worth/popularity being higher also has a similar effect (Refer to Section 2.3). Thus, all clubs and leagues have been given a ranking to signify its competition/stature, with both given ranks to act as proxy (Refer to Section 4.1). League Rank for a given season is also included, considering scenarios such as whether a player's performances were detrimental to the rise of the team. 90s (i.e., entire games played) is another metric included to incorporate

the consistency factor of a player and also to make sure that the normalized per90 metric is not misinterpreted by the model.

4.3 Injuries

Accounting injuries in such a model is a tedious task. Setting its proxy variable as just a Boolean does not address the severity of the injury, which is an important factor at how the player recovers. A Boolean variable would also not account for injury proneness of a player due to the lack of a quantitative variable. The approach utilised in this paper was to grade the severity of the injury and account for the number of games and days missed by the player. Grading injuries through official medical scales would have been difficult as it would require medical knowledge and expertise, which is beyond the scope of this paper. Thus, the severity of the injury was based on the number of days missed due to that infection. The following was the scale devised:

- Grade 1: Injuries which require less than 20 days to recover (such as infections, thigh issues, sprains, tightness, lack of fitness etc.)
- Grade 2: Injuries which require more than 20 and less than 50 days to recover (such as hamstring pulls, toe fractures etc.)
- Grade 3: Injuries which require more than 50 and less than 75 days to recover (such as hamstring tears, pulled calves etc.)
- Grade 4: Injuries which require more than 75 and less than 100 days to recover (such as shoulder and arm fractures, ankle fracture etc.)
- Grade 5: Injuries which require more than 100 days to recover (usual season ending injuries such as ACL and MCL tears)

This was followed by taking averages of all the injury metrics per season to account for different injuries and the frequency of it faced by every player.

5 Methodology

5.1 Overview

To achieve estimates with higher precision, traditional methods will be avoided, as in comparison to ML models, they provide lower accuracy. ML models differ over techniques but since the aim of this thesis is to get market values while optimizing its precision, it seems optimal to run different models and compare their accuracies. Models which will be applied are Random Forests (Breiman, 2001), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) (Chen & Guestrin, 2016) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) (Gonz, 2005). Venturing into an approach of deep learning models such as Neural Networks (NNs) (Bishop, 1995) can be considered but will not be dealt with in this paper due to its complexity and computational expense.

Oladipupo (2010) claims that SVMs are a ‘close cousin’ to multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural networks and even saying that a Sigmoid kernel-based SVM is equivalent to a two layer MLP neural networks. Information as such is crucial as neural networks, despite its precision, has its set of flaws (black-box design, i.e. they do not highlight/provide insights into importance of any feature, computationally intensive). MLP NNs also fail to model temporal relations, implying it cannot be used in this paper due to the data being longitudinal. To account for possible temporal effects, Recurrent NNs (Medsker & Jain, 2001) can be applied to learn sequential/time-varying effects too, but due to the sheer computational resources required it will be utilized in this paper but can be applied in future works.

The procedure followed in this paper involves developing separate models for Random Forest, XGBoost and Support Vector Regression (Drucker et al., 1996) for the two separate datasets. However, the approach regarding SVR will be a tad bit different due to the excessive computational cost required to run a kernel-based SVR on a large-scale dataset. Therefore, the approach now adopted is that of linear SVR (LSVR) which provides results comparable to kernel-based SVR but with

far more efficient training time and no large-scale accommodating struggle (Ho & Lin, 2012). Every model will have thorough hyperparameter tuning to ensure best fit possible. Furthermore, these models will be segregated further on the basis of their feature selection algorithms, followed by a comparison of their accuracies.

5.2 Feature Selection

Feature selection is required to deal with redundant and irrelevant features in the dataset and obtain a subset of features which are directly responsible for the accuracy of the predictions of the ML models. Redundancy can be originated from the correlation matrices, with Figure 14 and Figure 15 illustrating the same for the goalkeeper and the non-gokeeper dataset respectively. A heatmap has been used to make it easier to understand such huge matrices. The correlation matrix for the goalkeepers is much cooler (i.e. blue in colour) in comparison to the other players, indicating lesser number of features having high correlation among them.

This can be explained due to two reasons; firstly, the goalkeeper metrics are far simpler and more distinct in comparison to non-gokeeping performance metrics and secondly, the difference in the number of features (45 vs 138) does affect the possible interactions between the features, with the non-gokeeping metrics being more prone to having similar effects and therefore higher correlations. For instance, passing metrics which are differentiated on the basis of distance showcase high correlation due to similar effects derived from it, originating from the same core action of passing. Correlations are not of prime concern as this paper focuses on prediction rather than interpretation, but due to the computational costs involved and the potential yet slight effect it can have on the accuracy of the model, feature selection needs to be incorporated.

Feature selection becomes essential for this paper due to the number of features included in both the datasets being a large number. Remarkably enough, feature selection enables faster computing as higher number of features do impose a

Figure 14: Correlation Matrix of the features in the goalkeeper data

Figure 15: Correlation Matrix of the features in the non-goalkeeper dataset

strain on the computational resources available. It can be broadly divided into 3 different sects; Filter, Wrapper and Embedded methods, with Wrapper method considered to provide the most accurate results in comparison to the rest, but the payoff is that of computational cost. Unlike Filter methods which are independent of the learning algorithm of the ML model, Wrapper methods incorporate it along with interacting with the classifier(or in this paper's instance, regressor). Within the Wrapper methods, the most popular methods are sequentially based, such as forward selection and backward selection which start from the top or bottom respectively and including/removing features sequentially. Once a feature is removed, it cannot be included in the local optima search again. This drawback of Sequential methods can be detrimental to the performance features as sequential exclusion can affect the interactions between the features, thus requiring the need of a more stochastic approach for robust outcomes.

5.3 Metaheuristic Algorithms

Metaheuristic Algorithms are optimization algorithms which utilise stochastic components to optimize functions. A term coined by Glover (1986), with meta- meaning beyond or high level, metaheuristics perform far better than simple heuristics as they are able to do a trade-off between local search and global optima. The two essential components in every metaheuristic algorithm are exploration and exploitation (Blum & Roli, 2001). Exploration refers to expanding the solution space as far as possible to search on the global scale and exploitation refers to utilizing positive feedback in to narrow down the search in specific local regions based on the best solution at the current iteration. Metaheuristic algorithms can be applied to feature selection too, with the objective function being maximising the fit of the model.

Figure 16: Crossover between two chromosomes, (Holland, 1992)

5.3.1 Genetic Algorithm

The first metaheuristic algorithm applied for feature selection is the Genetic Algorithm (GA). Holland (1992) proposed an algorithm which mimicked Darwin's theory of Survival of the Fittest. Organisms evolve through 2 methods: natural selection and reproduction. The initial method decides which member of that organism's cohort survives to reproduce and reproduction ensures mixing of the genes, with occasionally mutation occurring which modifies the chromosome of the offspring. Population is then arranged as binary string (in 1s and 0s), rating each string based on the result produced and assessed by whatever score parameter deemed appropriate (dependent on the problem). Higher quality ones will reproduce, and lower quality ones perish, with mating process producing strings with different features due to the variety of combination and also due to the mutation that is witnessed.

Prior to this, the population of the chromosomes is initialized randomly. Fitness of each such chromosome is calculated and based on its value. A probability for the crossover of their attributes is chosen and applied to the two chosen chromosomes

to produce a new offspring. Similarly, a mutation probability is chosen to account for robustness and to avoid a uniform population being formed, which is then applied to the offspring to generate the finalized offspring, which is then placed in the newly created population, with the process repeating till the new population is complete. GA excels at exploring large spaces for the optimal situation, due to its attribute of implicit parallelism, also dealing with non-linear problems.

The operators involved in GA include encoding (i.e. coding of the dataset into a chromosome format), fitness function, selection format, crossovers and mutation, each with various methods to choose from dependent on the dataset and other related factors. For encoding, Binary Encoding is the one chosen for the feature selection approach. as it is the frequent approach applied, providing generally faster rates of crossover and mutation rates implementations. It encompasses almost all datasets except extremely complicated ones such as engineering design problems (due to epistasis i.e. overlapping effect on one gene due to the other genes witnessing change) (Katoch et al., 2021).

A fitness function is required to determine which chromosome survives and which perishes. Since the aim of the feature selection is to maintain or increase the predictive capabilities of the ML model whilst reducing the feature space, it would be a maximization problem with the aim of increasing R^2 . The function will also include a penalty to penalize higher number of features included, thus making the fitness function (Equation (1)):

$$R^2 \times \left(1 - 0.3 \times \frac{\text{Number of Selected Features}}{\text{Total Features}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where 0.3 is the coefficient of penalty.

Selection or the reproduction method chosen was based on the pro and cons of all methods done by Katoch et al. (2021) (refer to Figure 17). Rank and SUS seemed the best approaches but are computationally expensive. The Roulette

Selection Techniques	Pros	Cons
Roulette wheel	Easy to implement Simple Free from Bias	Risk of Premature convergence Depends upon variance present in the fitness function
Rank	Preserve diversity Free from Bias	Slow convergence Sorting required Computationally Expensive
Tournament	Preserve diversity Parallel Implementation No sorting required	Loss of diversity when the tournament size is large
Boltzmann Stochastic Universal Sampling	Global optimum achieved Fast Method Free from Bias	Computationally Expensive Premature convergence
Elitism	Preserve best Individual in population	Best individual can be lost due to crossover and mutation operators

Figure 17: Comparison of different selection techniques (Katoch et al., 2021)

Wheel approach seemed the simplest but was the most prone to convergence and the errors it causes due to its stochastic format. Tournament was the format chosen as the only essential drawback in it occurred only if the tournament was size large. Maintaining a small tournament size (in this case 3) does not cause such issues to arise and also maintains the diversity of the parents. The process involves selecting the fittest chromosomes from each of the random subsets initialized and then proceeding with reproduction.

Crossover operators refer to how the genes of the parents will be combined to generate an offspring. Crossover operators do differ in implementation with Partially Matched Crossover (PMX) being the most popular operator with better performance than the rest of the operators. However, it also faces premature convergence which could lead to suboptimal outcomes. A single point crossover would be ideal due to its easy application, but the method is far too simplistic to maintain the diversity. A two-point crossover is deemed to be a perfect middle ground, with its implementation similar to the illustration in Figure 18, leading to it being implemented in this feature selection model. Regarding mutation, it was felt that tampering with the string using Displacement and Scramble would cause disturbance in the population and thus a simple inversion mechanism or bit-flip is applied. In this operator, there are odds that a random bit in the string is flipped (a 1 becomes a 0 and a 0 becomes a 1).

Figure 18: Genetic information swapping after a two-point crossover(Katoch et al., 2021)

5.3.2 Particle Swarm Optimization

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is another evolutionary metaheuristic algorithm that will be used for feature selection for the SVR model. PSO was proposed and developed by Kennedy and Eberhart (1995). Also tied to genetic algorithms due to the evolutionary linkages of this method, it bases itself on the swarm patterns witnessed in organisms such as bird flocking and fish schooling.

The cornfield model designed by Heppner is used to forage the swarming or flocking behaviour of the birds. A plane is assumed where a cornfield is located and the birds or the particles are dispersed randomly. The coordinates of the cornfield are assumed to be (x_0, y_0) and the position and velocity coordinates of each bird is (x, y) and (v_x, v_y) respectively. The distance between these coordinates is used to measure the performance of the bird's current position and speed, thus further the bird the better performance and vice versa. The second assumption is that the birds have ability to memorize the best position it ever reached being denoted by $pbest$, a is a velocity constant, $rand$ is any random number between $[0,1]$. The change in velocity is then set according to the following (Wang et al., 2018):

$$\text{if } x > pbest_x, v_x = v_x - rand \times a, \text{ otherwise, } v_x = v_x + rand \times a \quad (2)$$

$$\text{if } y > pbest_y, v_y = v_y - rand \times a, \text{ otherwise, } v_y = v_y + rand \times a \quad (3)$$

The final assumption is that birds can communicate and now every bird knows and memorizes the best location known by the swarm so far, denoted as $gbest$. Taking b as the velocity constant, the rules are updated as follows :

$$\text{if } x > gbest_x, v_x = v_x - rand \times b, \text{ otherwise, } v_x = v_x + rand \times b \quad (4)$$

$$\text{if } y > gbest_y, v_y = v_y - rand \times b, \text{ otherwise, } v_y = v_y + rand \times b \quad (5)$$

A higher value of a/b results in birds reaching the cornfield much too quickly and vice versa for lower values. After trial and error, the basic PSO algorithm was formed:

$$v_x = v_x + 2 \times rand \times (pbest_x - x) + 2 \times rand \times (gbest_x - x) \quad (6)$$

$$x = x + v_x \quad (7)$$

In optimization terms, every particle/bird is a potential solution for the given problem in a d-dimensional solution space, with the ability to memorize its optimal position along that of the swarm, and thus memorize its velocity. With the ability to communicate, the combined information is used to adjust the velocity which calculates the new position of the particles on the plane, with them changing

positions until they reach the optimal point. A flowchart illustration (see Figure 19) presents this in a much more precise format.

However, this initial version of the algorithm was not the effective and a modification was introduced (Shi & Eberhart, 1998). The idea behind was that every particle, other than the particle which was at the global best position (and therefore having a velocity of 0), would be flying towards its own weighted centroid of its self-best position and that of the swarm's. In the initial equation, the c_1 and c_2 constants of velocity are taken to be 2 as the average of it would be 1, with the swarm statistically contracting to the global best position and by the time another particle takes over the swarm has already statistically contracted to the new global best position. So, unless the previous velocity variable (v_x) is factored in, the PSO resembles more of a local search. Thus, an inertia weight is included to balance between the local and global search. This modified method is the PSO algorithm which is implemented widely and used in this paper. The equation with the inertia weight (ω) become (Equations (8), (9)):

$$v_{i,t+1}^d = \omega * v_{i,t+1}^d + c_1 * rand * (p_{i,t}^d - x_{i,t}^d) + c_2 * rand * (p_{g,t}^d - x_{g,t}^d) \quad (8)$$

$$x_{i,t}^d = x_{i,t}^d + v_{i,t+1}^d \quad (9)$$

Shi and Eberhart (1998) further discussed choosing the optimal inertia weight (ω). They ran computer simulations taking different measures of ω , ranging from 0 to 1.5, running 4000 iterations each. Failure was defined as the inability of finding a global optimum within those 4000 iterations. Figure 20 illustrates the results witnessed, with 0 and 1.5 being highly prone to failure whereas values close to 1 (i.e. a range of 0.8 to 1.2), seem the best choices. 1 is considered to be the default value for ω and for the feature selection we will proceed with the default value.

Figure 19: Flowchart illustration of the process of the PSO algorithm (Wang et al., 2018)

Figure 20: Graphical depiction of failures witnessed per different weights (Shi & Eberhart, 1998)

The other parameters that are to be adjusted are the cognitive (c_1) and social (c_2) factor. Cognitive factor is the constant that affects the velocity of the particle based on own best position and thus termed cognitive factor. Social factor is the constant that affects the velocity based on the swarm's global best position, termed as social due to the communication that occurs between the particles. 2 is considered to be the generally accepted values for c_1 and c_2 , which make the search cover the region centred in $pbest$ and $gbest$. Carlisle and Dozier (2001) tested and found values 2.8 and 1.3 for c_1 and c_2 respectively to be better parameters but Kennedy (1997) tested the extremities, one with only the cognitive factor and one with only the social factor. The results suggested the criticality of each factor in the successful optimization of each solve but was unable to provide any definite conclusions about the asymmetry between the factors. With lack of clarity on its impact on the search region, default values of 2 were chosen for both c_1 and c_2 .

5.3.3 Ant Colony Optimization

Another algorithm associated with swarm intelligence; Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) utilizes the real life foraging behaviour of ants to develop a path towards a food source. Deneubourg et al. (1990) ran an experiment on Argentine ants, surrounding the ant nest with two bridges on the opposite ends, with both bridges equidistantly leading to food (see Figure 21). Initially, ants did not show movement

Figure 21: Deneubourg's bridge (a) and Goss' Bridge (b) (Dorigo et al., 2006)

but were rather exploring the nest's boundary. Soon after, ant pheromone trails were on both the bridges but faintly. Gradually, due to random fluctuations of the ants' explorations, one bridge had more pheromone deposits than the other and thus attracting more ants. The pheromone trails on the other bridge had evaporated and now the entire colony had converged to using a singular bridge. Exploiting positive feedback (known as autocatalysis) from other ants can allow them to choose the optimal route to the food source.

Goss et al. (1989)'s experiment had one bridge longer in distance than the other (refer to Figure 21). In this experiment, the random/stochastic fluctuations were reduced further as the ant which stumbled on the shorter bridge returned to the nest earlier too, due to the pheromone trail they had just built. This time, the convergence was must faster due to the quicker development of the pheromone trails. Goss built a model based on this observation, taking m_1 ants taking first bridge and m_2 ants taking the second bridge, the probability p_1 of an ant choosing the first bridge is:

$$p_1 = \frac{(m_1 + k)^h}{(m_1 + k)^h + (m_2 + k)^h} \quad (10)$$

where k and h are to be fitted and $p_2 = 1 - p_1$. Monte Carlo simulations showed a good fit when $k = 20$ and $h = 2$.

On the basis of this autocatalytic process, ACO was established by Dorigo et al.

(2006) as a metaheuristic. ACO iterates over three separate phases, with the first being termed *ConstructAntSolutions*. In this phase, a set of m artificial ants proceeds with the construction of solutions from the finite solution space C . The initial partial solution space S^P is empty, appended later by adding a feasible solution, originating from the set $N(S^P) \subset C$ (i.e. a set of solutions which do not violate the constraints). This set can thus be regarded as walk on the construction graph $G_c = (V,E)$ with V being the vertices and E being the edges.

The probability of the ant making a choice of component c_j (based on the pheromone probability equation, refer to equation number) is proportional to $\tau_j^\alpha \cdot \eta_j^\beta$, where τ_j is the pheromone value of the corresponding component (j) and η_j is the heuristic information of j . α and β are the parameters which control the relative importance of the pheromone value and heuristic information, adjusting between exploitation and exploration (Dorigo & Blum, 2005). The probability of c_j [only if $c_j \in N(S^P)$] would be:

$$P(c_j) = \frac{\tau_j^\alpha * \eta_j^\beta}{\sum_{c_j \in N(S^P)} [\tau_j^\alpha * \eta_j^\beta]} \quad (11)$$

The τ_j is updated to associate higher quality solutions and decrease the lower quality ones and for the latter to occur, a pheromone evaporation (ρ) is set. An update of τ_j is derived using the Equation (12):

$$\tau_j \leftarrow (1 - \rho) * \sum_k^m \Delta \tau_j^k \quad (12)$$

where m is the total number of ants with $\Delta \tau_j^k$ being the quantity of pheromone deposited by ant k on the feature/component j , its formula being:

$$\Delta\tau_j^k = \frac{Q}{L_k} \quad (13)$$

where Q is a constant and L_k is the quality of the solution concocted by ant k (Dorigo & Blum, 2005). These phases are then repeated until the fixed amount of iterations have lapsed or convergence. The parameters for ACO algorithm were chosen using offline tuning which selection through a process of trial-and-error (Stützle et al., 2010). ρ was set at 0.5 to ensure that pheromone trails do not disappear quickly in case an ant stumbles up on that feature j again in another iteration. Values for α and β are set as 1 and 2 respectively and due to the high number of features, β is set at a higher value to allow for more exploration of the features rather than autocatalysis.

5.3.4 Dwarf Mongoose Optimization

Dwarf Mongoose Optimization (DMO) is a relatively novel metaheuristic algorithm developed by Agushaka et al. (2022), inspired by the foraging nature of dwarf mongooses. Dwarf mongooses, *Helogale*, are commonly found in the African Savannah, living in family groups led by a matriarch (or an alpha bond). The hierarchical structure of the mongooses has the females outrank the males and the younglings outrank their older counterparts. The group is divided into roles such as guards, babysitters, scouts and attackers.

Due to the smaller frameworks than other predators, dwarf mongooses prey spectrum involves smaller mammals, insects, rodents etc. Such preys are unpredictable to find and thus require an extensive search for an individual to find a fulfilling meal. They have adopted a seminomadic approach, opting to forage stretches of the grasslands for foraging preys and rarely ever returning to the same sleeping mound: enabling lower odds of prey depletion. The foraging involves cohesion, which is propelled by communication using short nasal “peeps” at 2 kHz by the

Figure 22: Pictorial Representation of the foraging behaviour utilized in DMO (Agushaka et al., 2022)

alpha female Rasa (1972). However, the distance covered is dependent on factors such as the total number of mongooses, babysitting and predators. The group ascertains a few mongooses to serve as babysitters and look after the younglings, until the alpha group returns midday, exchanging roles with them and resuming the scouting of food source and the scouters seeking for new mounds.

The DMO algorithm implements this foraging behaviour, beginning with initializing the population and dividing them into the alpha group, babysitters and the scouts. The alpha group will proceed with the foraging and begin with the scouting

after the babysitter exchange criterium is fulfilled. This configured for by computing average sleeping mound value for each iteration and dependency on this value determines the next phase for the mongoose. The alpha female (α) is determined using a probabilistic method based upon on the fitness score (fit_i) as shown in Equation (14).

$$\alpha = \frac{fit_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n fit_i} \quad (14)$$

The number of mongooses in the alpha group is derived from $n - bs$, where n is the total mongoose population and bs is the number of babysitters. Potential food source candidates (X_{i+1}) are calculated using Equation (15)

$$X_{i+1} = X_i + \phi * peep \quad (15)$$

where phi is a random number between $[-1,1]$ and $peep$ is the short nasal sound made by the alpha female (α) to communicate and lead the group. In a similar manner, the sleeping mound value (sm_i) of each iteration is calculated using fit_i and the average sleeping mound value (φ) is derived from it as seen in Equations (16) and (17)

$$sm_i = \frac{fit_{i+1} + fit_i}{\max |fit_{i+1}, fit_i|} \quad (16)$$

$$\varphi = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n sm_i}{n} \quad (17)$$

The next phase is scouting of a new sleeping mound, which needs to be a new mound due to their behaviour of not returning to a previously utilized sleeping mound, therefore ensuring exploration. The movement is modelled as either a successful or failed evaluation of locating a new mound, and hence dependent on the performance of the mongooses; with the logic being further the distance, the higher the probability of finding a new mound to occupy. The scout mongoose is simulated as:

$$X_{i+1} = \begin{cases} X_i - CF \cdot \phi \cdot \text{rand} \cdot [X_i - \vec{M}] & \text{if } \varphi_{i+1} > \varphi_i \\ X_i + CF \cdot \phi \cdot \text{rand} \cdot [X_i - \vec{M}] & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

Where *rand* is a random number between [0.1] and $CF = (1 - \frac{\text{iter}}{\text{Maxiter}})^{(2 \frac{\text{iter}}{\text{Maxiter}})}$ is the parameter which accounts for the volatility in the movement of the mongooses, inversely proportional to the number of iterations. $\vec{M} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{X_i * sm_i}{X_i}$ is the vector that computes the movement of the group to the new sleeping mound. The first instance in this case is exploration as the condition implies that the value of the sleeping mound found in the new iteration is higher than the mound found in the previous iteration. Unlike the previously used algorithms used in this paper, DMO has only one parameter to tune (i.e. the number of babysitters) making it effective yet easy to implement in comparison to its counterparts.

6 Empirical Results

6.1 Model Evaluation

Evaluating predictive models is a much-conflicted topic in research, with no definite evaluation metric considered to be the universally best approach. These metrics aim to measure the errors made by the model, evaluating it on that basis.

The metrics utilized in classification (such AUC, F1 score, Confusion Matrix etc.) problems differ from the ones used in regression (R^2 , MSE, RMSE etc.), yet the problems arise in all. Researchers argue that the popular metrics used can also be subjected to scrutiny. However, one metric which does receive constant scrutiny and is not even included in the top 4 metrics used in surveys is R^2 (Botchkarev, 2019).

J. Li (2017) warns against the usage of R^2 to assess predictive accuracy of numerical data because it is biased, insufficient and misleading. This claim originates due to the metric not being calculated on the difference between the predicted and observed values, followed him mathematically showing the issues with it. It has been included for this paper for the model evaluation as we did utilize it as the main fitness score for the metaheuristic algorithms as it was meant to make a features subset which would hold high explanatory power for the target variable, but it will not be used to assess prediction accuracy. Metrics which are based on the difference between predicted and absolute values (i.e. all the squared/standard error metrics) are generally preferred but they do have their own share of concerns. MSE (Mean Square Error) and MAE (Mean Absolute Error) are prone to outliers due to its dependence on unit/scale of the target variable and variance, especially MSE with heavy discouragement towards its usage found in the literature in the early 2000s. However, Chai and Draxler (2014) debunked and revitalized the usage of MSE metrics, however stating that they do not contend it to be superior to MAE, rather recommending combining both the metrics to derive meaningful conclusions.

Tables 1 and 2 evaluate all the models with the criteria mentioned above and also lists the number of features selected in each of the models, where the suffix are the feature selection method and the prefix being the models where ‘XGB’ is XGBoost, ‘RFR’ is Random Forest Regressor and ‘LSVR is Linear SVR’. All the “Base-“ models include all the features available in the dataset (i.e. 45 features in the goalkeeper dataset and 138 features in the rest of the players dataset). Rest of the models have the number of features selected by its corresponding metaheuristic algorithm.

Table 1: Performance Comparison of the Machine Learning Models (Non-Goalkeepers)

Model	RMSE	MSE	MAE	MAPE	R ²	Features Selected
Base-XGB	9.34×10^6	8.73×10^{13}	5.04×10^6	1.61	0.66	138
GA-XGB	9.08×10^6	8.24×10^{13}	4.98×10^6	1.65	0.68	39
PSO-XGB	9.83×10^6	9.66×10^{13}	5.36×10^6	1.74	0.62	79
ACO-XGB	9.21×10^6	8.48×10^{13}	4.99×10^6	1.67	0.67	34
DMO-XGB	9.18×10^6	8.43×10^{13}	4.93×10^6	1.54	0.67	48
Base-RFR	9.57×10^6	9.16×10^{13}	5.55×10^6	2.49	0.64	138
GA-RFR	9.02×10^6	8.14×10^{13}	5.14×10^6	2.00	0.68	25
PSO-RFR	9.22×10^6	8.51×10^{13}	5.31×10^6	2.15	0.67	64
ACO-RFR	9.04×10^6	8.17×10^{13}	5.13×10^6	2.10	0.68	15
DMO-RFR	9.26×10^6	8.57×10^{13}	5.29×10^6	2.12	0.66	29
Base-LSVR	1.15×10^7	1.33×10^{14}	7.29×10^6	3.84	0.48	138
GA-LSVR	1.17×10^7	1.36×10^{14}	7.39×10^6	3.93	0.46	37
PSO-LSVR	1.15×10^7	1.33×10^{14}	7.30×10^6	3.87	0.48	91
ACO-LSVR	1.15×10^7	1.33×10^{14}	7.29×10^6	3.84	0.48	133
DMO-LSVR	1.16×10^7	1.34×10^{14}	7.32×10^6	3.86	0.47	39

Note: Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

Table 2: Performance Comparison of the Machine Learning Models (Goalkeepers)

Model	RMSE	MSE	MAE	MAPE	R ²	Features Selected
Base-XGB	7.38×10^6	5.45×10^{13}	3.39×10^6	1.71	0.59	45
GA-XGB	7.42×10^6	5.51×10^{13}	3.59×10^6	1.71	0.58	17
PSO-XGB	7.11×10^6	5.05×10^{13}	3.39×10^6	1.65	0.61	22
ACO-XGB	7.16×10^6	5.12×10^{13}	3.37×10^6	1.69	0.61	22
DMO-XGB	7.05×10^6	4.97×10^{13}	3.26×10^6	1.60	0.62	16
Base-RFR	7.69×10^6	5.91×10^{13}	4.19×10^6	3.30	0.55	45
GA-RFR	7.27×10^6	5.28×10^{13}	3.96×10^6	3.06	0.60	11
PSO-RFR	7.36×10^6	5.42×10^{13}	4.03×10^6	3.25	0.59	25
ACO-RFR	7.31×10^6	5.34×10^{13}	4.07×10^6	3.35	0.59	22
DMO-RFR	7.25×10^6	5.26×10^{13}	3.89×10^6	3.10	0.60	11
Base-LSVR	9.69×10^6	9.40×10^{13}	5.57×10^6	5.89	0.29	45
GA-LSVR	9.57×10^6	9.16×10^{13}	5.84×10^6	6.49	0.30	13
PSO-LSVR	9.94×10^6	9.89×10^{13}	5.88×10^6	6.59	0.25	11
ACO-LSVR	9.95×10^6	9.92×10^{13}	5.87×10^6	6.56	0.25	10
DMO-LSVR	9.59×10^6	9.20×10^{13}	5.86×10^6	6.47	0.30	12

Note: Bold values indicate the best performance for each metric.

6.2 Non-Goalkeepers Dataset

In Table 1, the best values for each of the evaluation metrics for the non-goalkeeper models are boldened to highlight them. In the terms of RMSE (Root Mean Square Error) and MSE, GA-RFR is the best performing model but with narrow margins. RMSE is used to scale back MSE to the unit of the target variable and make it interpretable. RMSE of 9.02×10^6 can be interpreted as the market value estimates (or predictions) having an error of approximately €9 million. This figure in itself might feel like a massive error margin, but it becomes important to recall that the dataset contains outliers such as highly talented players being valued at around the €100 million+ mark.

It should also be noted that most players are valued $< €10$ million, even the most valuable started their careers at mark which is accounted for through the temporal observations of each player's career (dependent on data availability). Thus, this RMSE could have a negative connotation for the lower-valued players but fortunately that is not the case. RMSE penalizes larger errors more and with values of players ranging from anywhere between €100k-100 million, contextually; it makes the given RMSE estimate a good measure to highlight better predictive accuracy. ACO-RFR follows in closely, with extremely similar RMSE and MSE to that of GA-RFR, but with lesser features selected (15 features selected v.s. 25 features selected), suggesting that the curse of dimensionality might be in play (Verleysen & François, 2005), but with an effect not that tremendous as can be seen with the Base models performing almost at par with the rest.

Surprisingly, the LSVR models were outperformed by the RFR and XGB models by a margin bigger than expected. One might argue that it can be potentially due to incorrect kernel selection, however rigorous hyperparameter tuning of both SVR and LSVR lead to the same output, with the kernel being linear in SVR. Kernel approximation using Nystrom and RBFSampler were to no avail either. Reasons causing this are not evident however it could potentially be due to outliers and perhaps inability to handle unbalanced temporal data, but this is all speculation

and could just simply be LSVR not suitable for this dataset.

MAE takes the absolute difference between the predicted and the actual values, not penalizing large error like the MSE, therefore making it less prone to outliers but does make it variance dependent. The lowest MAE among the models is that of DMO-XGB, outperforming GA-RFR and ACO-RFR. Its interpretation is similar to that of RMSE, indicating that the estimates of the DMO-XGB model have an average margin of error of €4.93 million. MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage Error) is a metric derived MAE relative to the actual value and displayed in a percentage format. MAPE values below 10% are considered to be a measure of high predictive accuracy (Anggrainingsih et al., 2015) and the MAPE values across the models are below 4%, indicating significantly high predictive accuracy in relative terms, with this approach being favorable to the amount and scale of the outliers of the target variable. DMO-XGB outperforms the others, exhibiting a value of 1.54%, which can be interpreted as the estimates are 1.54% off the value of the actuals. MAPE itself does face criticism, but it is primarily regarding target variables which can take the value of zero therefore building the metric upon an invalid value. This shortcoming of MAPE is avoided due to none of the market values being zero, making it a suitable evaluation metric for this paper.

Based on these metrics, there is a dilemma in choosing one of the models between GA-RFR and DMO-XGB, performing well with regards to squared errors and absolute errors respectively. Using R^2 as the deciding factor, GA-RFR would be achieving higher accuracy from 3 out of a possible 5, however due to the discussion above stacked up the notion of overfitting along with the vast range of the outliers, DMO-XGB should be the preferred model.

6.3 Goalkeepers Dataset

Unlike the rest of the players dataset, the models for the goalkeeper dataset (refer to Table 2) have a rather straightforward result. DMO-XGB outperforms all other

models on all the metrics (including R^2), making it the preferred model. However, general model behaviour is quite contrasting in this dataset, also serving as an instance of the misleading nature of the squared errors and R^2 .

RFR has almost similar levels of accuracy in comparison to that of the XGB models with R^2 lying between the range of 59%-61% (excluding Base-RFR), with similar RMSEs around the €7 million mark. It would be fair to assume that there is no significant difference between the XGB and the RFR models until you glance over to the absolute error metrics. Highest MAE value of the XGB models (GA-XGB) is still 300k less than the lowest MAE of the RFR models (DMO-RFR). MAPE metrics are even more contrasting with the lowest MAPE of the XGB models being around 3% whereas it does not even go beyond 1.8%. LSVR performs far worse relatively for this dataset, with exhibiting higher error margins for all the metrics.

6.4 Feature Importance

Understanding feature importance is not essential to the model accuracy, it is an approach to understand how the features are interacting and affecting the predictions. Feature importance does not exist for LSVRs due to it being a “black box” model. Random Forest and XGBoost models are both decision tree based and do support feature importance. The feature importance of the both DMO-XGB models are displayed alongside both the Base-XGB models in Table 3 and 4 for the non-goalkeepers and goalkeepers respectively.

In Table 3, the most important feature of the DMO-XGB model is the difference between non-penalty goals (npG) and xG per90, influencing 17% of the predictions, whereas for the base model it is the Total Progressive Passing Distance per90 accounting for a 34% impact on the estimates. One metric reflects shooting conversion quality, which usually associated with forwards and attacking midfielders and the other highlights buildup play, encompassing all positions in some way or the other. The measure is indicative of overperformance by a player, which

Table 3: Feature Importance of the Selected Machine Learning Models (Non-Goalkeepers)

Base-XGB	DMO-XGB
Total Progressive Passing Distance per90 (34.39)	npG-xG per90 (17.41)
Defensive SCA per90 (8.68)	Through Balls completed per90 (12.33)
Height (8.20)	GCA per90 (9.29)
Position (6.89)	Season (6.48)
xG p90 (3.71)	Goals/Shot on Target per90 (5.18)
GCA per90 (3.58)	Progressive Distance Carried per90 (4.92)
Shots on Target per90 (3.35)	Age (4.69)
Through Balls completed per90 (3.03)	npG/Shot per90 (3.61)
Live-ball Passes GCA per90 (2.82)	xAG per90 (3.13)
npG per90 (2.05)	Squad (2.69)
Pass Completion % (1.41)	League (2.58)
Season (1.30)	League Position (2.56)
Penalty Kicks Attempted per90 (1.17)	Passes Received per90 (2.20)
Take-Ons SCA per90 (1.14)	90s (2.00)
League (0.79)	Goals per90 (1.99)
League Position (0.78)	Touches per90 in the Attacking Penalty Area (1.74)
Squad (0.63)	Touches per90 in the Final Third (1.71)
Total Carrying Distance per 90 (0.63)	Short Passes Completed per90 (1.61)
Average Grade of Injury (0.61)	Average Grade of Injury (1.23)
Progressive Passes per90 (0.60)	Fouls Drawn per90 (1.04)

Note: Values in parentheses indicate the importance (in %) of the feature.

could be considered a one-time event and eventually regressing back to the mean, but accounting it over time could show consistent overperforming which just highlights the finishing ability of the player. However, having an influence of 34% on the estimates is rather peculiar, as it reduces the impact of other theoretically important variables (Refer to [Appendix](#) for definition of all the metrics).

Season having an importance of 6.48% in the DMO-XGB model, indicating temporal factors do affect market value estimates. DMO-XGB surprisingly exhibits no defensive metrics in the top 20 features at least, indicating either the metrics being too conflicting or the current metrics being suffice enough to estimate defensive players' market value accurately. 90s having 2% of an influence also affirms the claim made earlier regarding per90 normalizations, rewarding consistency. Squad, League and League Position having importances less than 3% each is a positive indication for players, as it highlights that performance-related and other metrics will have a higher impact on their values rather than the prestige of the squad

Table 4: Feature Importance of the Selected Machine Learning Models (Goalkeepers)

Base-XGB	DMO-XGB
Aerial Duels Won per90 (8.40)	Loose Balls Recovered per90 (19.22)
Goals Against per90 (7.39)	Squad (14.93)
League (6.60)	League (11.08)
Loose Balls Recovered per90 (5.20)	Total Minutes Played (8.43)
Height (5.16)	Height (7.88)
Total Minutes Played (4.99)	Wins per90 (7.71)
Percentage of Aerial Duels Win (4.71)	Age (6.71)
90s (4.67)	Losses per90 (5.95)
Squad (4.26)	Average Days Missed due to Injury (5.52)
Age (4.20)	Weight (4.24)

Note: Values in parentheses indicate the importance (in %) of the feature.

and the league alone. Average Grade of Injury having a minute impact (1.23%) is the only injury variable present, which would be appropriate due to the high correlation between all the injury metrics. No physical metrics is another intriguing observation.

In Table 4, top 10 features are taken for the models, with DMO-XGB having no goalkeeping metrics in the top 10 features. Its most important feature is Loose Balls Recovered per90 at 19%, perhaps indicating of the sweeping (i.e. rushing out behaviour) nature of the goalkeepers. The Base-XGB model has Aerial Duels Won per90 as its most important feature followed Goals Against per90, which are much more theoretically plausible features. Exclusion of those variables from the DMO-XGB can be potentially due to correlation with the rest or the algorithm found discrepancies with its consistency, thus excluding it. DMO-XGB also associates higher importance to Height than the Base Model (8% > 5%). It also shares similarities with the non-gokeeper dataset with importance for Minutes Played (similar to 90s) and Average Days Missed due to Injury (similar to Average Grade of Injury). However, DMO-XGB models the goalkeepers heavily based on team and team performance, reflected by Wins and Losses per 90 combining for around 16% importance (Refer to [Appendix](#) for definition of all the metrics).

Table 5: Highest Valued Players from the Non-Goalkeeper Testing Dataset

Name	Season	Predicted Value	Transfermarkt Value
Mohamed Salah	2018-19	123,948,180	150,000,000
Phil Foden	2021-22	116,722,490	85,000,000
Marcus Rashford	2019-20	114,803,990	80,000,000
Kylian Mbappe	2022-23	113,782,030	180,000,000
Kevin De Bruyne	2019-20	111,739,950	150,000,000
Jack Grealish	2022-23	105,570,730	70,000,000
Robert Lewandowski	2019-20	100,058,984	70,000,000
Lautaro Martinez	2020-21	97,262,800	70,000,000
Trent Alexander Arnold	2019-20	96,019,890	110,000,000
Vinicius Junior	2022-23	96,001,944	120,000,000

Note: All values are in Euros(€)

6.5 Player Predictions

Player estimates in this paper will be different than most of its contemporaries due to the inclusion of seasonal stats, therefore every season needs to be treated as a separate entity. For comparing the results, 2024 (or the 2024-25) season estimates will not be incorporated due to it being the ongoing season which is yet to finish (as of February 2025). Tables 5 and 6 display the top 10 highest valued players from both the datasets, which is topped by the Liverpool duo comprising of Mohamed Salah from the 2018-19 season being valued at around €123 million and Alisson from the same season being valued at €59 million. The top 10 results show no clear trend of overestimating or underestimating more, rather both situations are occurring almost alternatively. The estimates of the model bring about a balance to the grossly exaggerated prices from Transfermarkt as well. Ederson occurring thrice in the top 10 list due to random generation of the test set, also serves a path to show how the model treats temporal changes far better than the Transfermarkt ones.

Tables 7,8,9,10 illustrate the market values of players that were overestimated and underestimated for both the datasets. Overestimated market values can be interpreted as players who perform well but go under the radar and thus exhibiting

Table 6: Highest Valued Players from the Goalkeeper Testing Dataset

Name	Season	Predicted Value	Transfermarkt Value
Alisson	2018-19	59,401,036	65,000,000
Thibaut Courtois	2021-22	56,869,616	65,000,000
Ederson	2020-21	51,095,576	56,000,000
Ederson	2021-22	43,132,536	50,000,000
Marc Andre Ter Stegen	2020-21	37,148,190	75,000,000
Alex Meret	2022-23	37,145,290	13,000,000
Ederson	2023-24	33,386,934	27,000,000
Gregor Kobel	2022-23	33,124,270	25,000,000
Jan Oblak	2018-19	32,935,462	80,000,000
Kepa Arrizabalaga	2019-20	30,035,648	60,000,000

Note: All values are in Euros(€)

a lower value by Transfermarkt while having high potential or it could be due to weightage of the metrics not aligning with the player’s pre-existing positive metrics, and vice versa for the interpretation of underestimated players. Some of these estimations can be explained due to certain events or known information. For instance, Summerville is valued at €60 million in 2023-24 despite being in the Championship (Second Division of English Football) that season due to the absurd season he had from an attacking output purview. Alex Meret is valued at €37 million during the 2022-23 due to the pivotal role he played in enabling Napoli to win the league title while before that season he was not even a starter. Eriksen is valued at €20 million in 2019-20, despite Transfermarkt valuing him at €90 million, due to a relatively worse performance that season along with injuries and mid-season transfer. Relatively worse performance is a reason that can be applied to Rashford, Lukaku, Icardi and Vlahovic as well. Oblak being underestimated is not due to his bad performances but rather team dependent. It can also be attributed to the nature of the model to not exaggerate the price of the goalkeepers.

Table 7: Top 5 Overestimated Players from the Non-Goalkeeper Testing Dataset

Name	Season	Predicted Value	Transfermarkt Value
Crysencio Summerville	2023-24	60,208,860	18,000,000
Oleksandr Zinchenko	2022-23	73,126,290	32,000,000
Dani Ceballos	2022-23	48,366,350	9,000,000
Nathan Ake	2022-23	67,292,100	30,000,000
Mason Greenwood	2019-20	55,500,864	20,000,000

Note: All values are in Euros(€)

Table 8: Top 5 Underestimated Players from the Non-Goalkeeper Testing Dataset

Name	Season	Predicted Value	Transfermarkt Value
Christian Eriksen	2019-20	22,117,686	90,000,000
Mauro Icardi	2019-20	20,015,192	75,000,000
Marcus Rashford	2021-22	32,898,608	85,000,000
Romelu Lukaku	2018-19	33,339,524	85,000,000
Dusan Vlahovic	2022-23	30,029,462	80,000,000

Note: All values are in Euros(€)

Table 9: Top 5 Overestimated Players from the Goalkeeper Testing Dataset

Name	Season	Predicted Value	Transfermarkt Value
Alex Meret	2022-23	37,145,290	13,000,000
Fernando Muslera	2010-11	25,474,982	8,500,000
Ivan Provedel	2022-23	20,559,992	7,000,000
Thibaut Courtois	2011-12	18,087,876	6,000,000
Mathew Ryan	2017-18	16,800,464	5,000,000

Note: All values are in Euros(€)

Table 10: Top 5 Underestimated Players from the Goalkeeper Testing Dataset

Name	Season	Predicted Value	Transfermarkt Value
Jan Oblak	2019-20	28,652,836	100,000,000
Gianluigi Donnarumma	2021-22	11,959,713	65,000,000
Jan Oblak	2018-19	32,935,462	80,000,000
Marc Andre Ter Stegen	2020-21	37,148,190	75,000,000
David de Gea	2019-20	27,526,956	60,000,000

Note: All values are in Euros(€)

7 Conclusion

Market value estimation is a nuanced concept which requires domain knowledge and vast amount of data to proceed with the estimation. Crowd market value estimations done through forums such as Transfermarkt have been popular within the football community to assess and evaluate players. However, predictive modelling would be a far better approach to evaluate players due to its ability to encompass several features/variables which the “wisdom of the crowd” often fails to undertake. Pairing metaheuristic algorithms for feature selection with ML models to remove redundant features to enhance predictive accuracy is a practice that should be popularized further. The DMO-XGB model created here can be used to understand a player’s worth on the pitch. The estimated values generated can be viewed as thresholds by clubs to determine how much money should be spent on the transfer of that player theoretically (barring contract status, selling club demands and other transfer related variables). Several researchers have worked upon modelling market values of players and also attempt to compare it to the crowd values, with many new advances heading towards better predictivity. Building its foundation on that basis, this paper brings about novelty through a change in approach. Performance metrics have been utilized in previous papers at smaller scales, whilst this research prioritizes it, using it extensively which involves. Injury metrics need to be developed further to assess their impact in more nuanced situation, however the injury metrics used here are a step towards it.

Appendix: Glossary for Performance Metrics

General Metrics

Metric	Description
Season	Year in which the leagues run
Age	Age at season start
Country	Country of the league
Comp	Name of the league
LgRank	Finish within the league
90s	Total minutes played divided by 90

Source: (FBref.com, [n.d.](#))

Miscellaneous Stats

Metric	Description
CrdY	Yellow Cards
CrdR	Red Cards
2CrdY	Second Yellow Card
Fls	Fouls Committed
Fld	Fouls Drawn
Off	Offsides
PKwon	Penalty Kicks Won
PKcon	Penalty Kicks Conceded
OG	Own Goals
Recov	Number of loose balls recovered
Won	Aerial Duels Won
Lost	Aerial Duels Lost
Won%	Percentage of aerial duels won

Source: (FBref.com, [n.d.](#))

Shooting Metrics

Metric	Description
Gls	Goals scored or allowed
Sh	Shots Total (excluding penalty kicks)
SoT	Shots on Target (excluding penalty kicks)
SoT%	Percentage of shots that are on target (excluding penalty kicks)
G/Sh	Goals per shot (excluding penalty kicks)
G/SoT	Goals per shot on target (excluding penalty kicks)
Dist	Average distance, in yards, from goal of all shots taken (excluding penalty kicks)
FK	Shots from Free Kicks
PK	Penalty Kicks Made
PKatt	Penalty Kicks Attempted
xG	Expected Goals, xG totals include penalty kicks, but do not include penalty shootouts (unless otherwise noted)
npG	Non-Penalty Expected Goals
npG/Sh	Non-Penalty Expected Goals per shot
G-xG	Goals - xG i.e. realized performance
np:G-xG	Non-Penalty Goals minus Non-Penalty Expected Goals

Source: (FBref.com, [n.d.](#))

Passing Metrics

Metric	Description
Cmp	Passes Completed, includes live ball passes (including crosses) as well as corner kicks, throw-ins, free kicks and goal kicks
Att	Passes Attempted, includes live ball passes (including crosses) as well as corner kicks, throw-ins, free kicks and goal kicks
Cmp%	Pass Completion Percentage
TotDist	Total distance, in yards, that completed passes have traveled in any direction
PrgDist	Progressive Distance, i.e. total distance, in yards, that completed passes have traveled towards the opponent's goal. Note: Passes away from opponent's goal are counted as zero progressive yards
Short_Cmp	Passes Completed between 5 and 15 yards
Short_Att	Passes Attempted between 5 and 15 yards
Short_Cmp%	Pass Completion Percentage between 5 and 15 yards
Medium_Cmp	Passes Completed between 15 and 30 yards
Medium_Att	Passes Attempted between 15 and 30 yards
Medium_Cmp%	Pass Completion Percentage between 15 and 30 yards
Long_Cmp	Passes Completed longer than 30 yards
Long_Att	Passes Attempted longer than 30 yards
Long_Cmp%	Pass Completion Percentage longer than 30 yards
Ast	Assists
xAG	Expected Assisted Goals, xG which follows a pass that assists a shot
xA	Expected Assists, The likelihood each completed pass becomes a goal assists given the pass type, phase of play, location and distance
A-xAG	Assists minus Expected Goals Assisted
KP	Key Passes, Passes that directly lead to a shot (assisted shots)
1/3	Completed passes that enter the final third (the pitch closest to the goal)
PPA	Completed passes into the Penalty Area (Opponent's)
CrsPA	Completed crosses into the Penalty Area (Opponent's)
PrgP	Completed passes that move the ball towards the opponent's goal line at least 10 yard from its furthest point in the last six passes, or any completed pass into the penalty area. Excludes passes from the defending 40% of the pitch

Pass Types

Metric	Description
Live	Live ball i.e. open play passes
Dead	Dead-ball passes i.e. passes from free kicks, corner kicks, kick offs, throw-ins and goal kicks
FK	Passes attempted from free kicks
TB	Through Balls, Completed pass sent between back defenders into open space
Sw	Switches, Passes that travel more than 40 yards of the width of the pitch
Crs	Crosses
TI	Throw-ins Taken
CK	Corner Kicks
In	Inswinging Corner Kicks
Out	Outswinging Corner Kicks
Str	Straight Corner Kicks
Off	Passes Offside
Blocks	Blocked by the opponent who was standing in the path

Source: (FBref.com, [n.d.](#))

Goal and Shot Creation

Metric	Description
SCA	Shot-Creating Actions: The two offensive actions directly leading to a shot, such as passes, take-ons and drawing fouls Note: A single player can receive credit for multiple actions and the shot-taker can also receive credit
SCA_PassLive	Completed live-ball passes that lead to a shot attempt
SCA_PassDead	Completed dead-ball passes that lead to a shot attempt
SCA_TO	Successful take-ons that lead to a shot attempt
SCA_Fld	Fouls drawn that lead to a shot attempt
SCA_Def	Defensive actions that lead to a shot attempt
GCA	Goal-Creating Actions: The two offensive actions directly leading to a goal, such as passes, take-ons and drawing fouls Note: A single player can receive credit for multiple actions and the shot-taker can also receive credit
GCA_PassLive	Completed live-ball passes that lead to a goal
GCA_PassDead	Completed dead-ball passes that lead to a goal
GCA_TO	Successful take-ons that lead to a goal
GCA_Sh	Shots that lead to another goal-scoring shot
GCA_Fld	Fouls drawn that lead to a goal
GCA_Def	Defensive actions that lead to a goal

Source: (FBref.com, [n.d.](#))

Defensive Actions

Metric	Description
Tkl	Number of players tackled
TklW	Tackles in which the tackler's team won possession of the ball
Def 3rd	Tackles in defensive third
Mid 3rd	Tackles in middle third
Att 3rd	Tackles in attacking third
Challenges_Tkl	Number of dribblers tackled
Challenges_Att	Number of unsuccessful challenges plus number of dribblers tackled
Challenges_Tkl%	% of Dribblers Tackled, dribblers tackled divided by number of attempts to challenge an opposing dribbler
Challenges_Lost	Number of unsuccessful attempts to challenge a dribbling player
Blocks	Number of times blocking the ball by standing in its path
Sh	Shots Blocked, number of times blocking a shot by standing in its path
Passes	Passes Blocked, number of times blocking a pass by standing in its path
Int	Interceptions
Tkl+Int	Number of players tackled plus number of interceptions
Clr	Clearances
Err	Mistakes leading to an opponent's shot

Source: (FBref.com, [n.d.](#))

Possession

Metric	Description
Touches	Number of times a player touched the ball Note: Receiving a pass, then dribbling, then sending a pass counts as one touch
Def Pen	Touches in defensive penalty area
Def 3rd	Touches in defensive third
Mid 3rd	Touches in middle third
Att 3rd	Touches in attacking third
Att Pen	Touches in attacking penalty area
Live	Live-ball touches
Att	Take-Ons Attempted, number of attempts to take on defenders while dribbling
Succ	Successful Take-Ons, number of defenders taken on successfully, by dribbling past them Note: Unsuccessful take-ons include attempts where the dribbler retained possession but was unable to get past the defender
Succ%	Percentage of Take-Ons Completed Successfully
Tkld	Number of times tackled by a defender during a take-on attempt
Tkld%	Percentage of time tackled by a defender during a take-on attempt
Carries	Number of times the player controlled the ball with their feet
TotDist	Total distance, in yards, a player moved the ball while controlling it with their feet, in any direction
PrgDist	Total distance, in yards, a player moved the ball while controlling it with their feet towards the opponent's goal
PrgC	Carries that move the ball towards the opponent's goal line at least 10 yards from its furthest point in the last six passes, or any carry into the penalty area
1/3	Carries that enter the third of the pitch closest to the goal
CPA	Carries into Penalty Area
Mis	Number of times a player failed when attempting to gain control of a ball
Dis	Number of times a player loses control of the ball after being tackled by an opposing player
Rec	Number of times a player successfully received a pass
PrgR	Progressive Passes Received

Source: (FBref.com, [n.d.](#))

Goalkeeping

Metric	Description
GA	Goals Against
SoTA	Shots on Target Against
Save%	(Shots on Target Against - Goals Against)/Shots on Target Against Note: Does not include penalty kicks
W	Wins
D	Draws
L	Losses
CS	Clean Sheets, full matches by goalkeeper where no goals are allowed
CS%	Percentage of matches that result in clean sheets
PKatt	Penalty Kicks Attempted
PKA	Penalty Kicks Allowed
PKsv	Penalty Kicks Saved
PKm	Penalty Kicks Missed
Save%	Penalty Save Percentage, Penalty Kick Goals Against/Penalty Kick Attempts

Source: (FBref.com, [n.d.](#))

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